

THE EFFECT OF USING BINAHONG LEAVES IN REDUCING THE INCIDENCE OF INFECTIONS IN PERINEAL WOUNDS

Nina Sunarti¹, Rikha Janahtul Khasanah²

¹Harum Nursing Academy Jakarta (INDONESIA)

²Harum Nursing Academy Jakarta (INDONESIA)

sunartinina2@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: The postpartum period (Post Partum) is the period that begun after the birth of the placenta and ends when the uterus returns to its pre-pregnancy state, which lasts for 6 weeks or 42 days. Perineal wounds are tears in the perineum that occur during childbirth and result in tissue tears. Kegel exercise is pubococcygeal muscle movements in the form of contracting and stretching. Vulva hygiene is the behavior of maintaining the cleanliness and health of the external genital organs (vulva) to prevent infection, by using a decoction of binahong leaves which contains flavonoids as an anti-inflammatory, analgesic and antioxidant. Objective: Prevent infection and speed up healing of episiotomy wounds after normal delivery. Methodology: data collection was done through interview, observation, physical examination and demonstration of vulva hygiene method using binahong leaves decoction and Kegel exercise. Results: In normal primiparous post partum mothers with episiotomy wounds, the vulva hygiene method using boiled binahong leaves and Kegel exercise can be applied so that the risk of infection in the episiotomy wound can be prevented. Conclusion: The vulva hygiene method using boiled binahong leaves twice a day during bath time, after urinating or after defecating and Kegel exercise can be done independently at home for normal primiparous postpartum mothers with episiotomy wounds.

Key words: *Postpartum period, Kegel exercise, binahong leaves*

1. INTRODUCTION

The birth process is something that mothers are really looking forward to, after waiting for about nine months of pregnancy, waiting for their baby is of course the most important thing for all mothers. After entering the labor period, mother will be faced with the postpartum period or also known as post partum. The postpartum period is at risk of dangers such as excessive bleeding, infection and other risks. Therefore, monitoring and supervision of anatomical and physiological changes during the postpartum period, appropriate care and support are very necessary to ensure the health and well-being of mother and baby.

During normal delivery, mother can experience injuries to the perineum due to an episiotomy or a tear in the birth canal. Perineal laceration is a wound in the muscular area covered by skin between the vaginal introitus and anus caused by tears due to childbirth. Complications that occur from perineal lacerations are delayed wound healing and even infection. The impacts that occur if wound healing is hampered include pain and fear of moving, which can cause many problems including uterine sub-involution, poor lochea expulsion, and post-partum hemorrhage which is the first cause of maternal death in Indonesia. Perineal wounds that are not handled properly will cause complications, such as

blood loss due to performing an episiotomy too early, infection due to contamination with urine and feces, dyspareunia, and hematoma. local causes infection so it needs to be treated properly. The treatment is to treat the wound well so that it doesn't get infected.

Based on research results, binahong leaves contain saponins, alkaloids and polyphenols, triterpenoids, flavonoids and essential oils. Saponin is a surface-active compound and has soap-like properties. Saponin stimulates the formation of collagen, a structural protein that plays a role in the wound healing process. Binahong leaves also contain oleanolic acid which has anti-inflammatory properties and can reduce pain in wounds. Binahong leaves contain antimicrobials which are theoretically effective in healing wounds by preventing infection and preventing the spread of wounds due to toxic bacteria. The antimicrobials in binahong leaves are reactive against several germs that cause infection, including *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* which is a dangerous germ in wounds and other infectious bacteria. The ascorbic acid content in binahong can increase resistance to infection, maintain mucous membranes and accelerate wound healing.

2. METHODOLOGY

The design used in preparing this research is through a case study with the aim of exploring the problem of the risk of episiotomy wound infection by providing vulva hygiene with binahong leaves and Kegel exercise. 10 {ten} respondents are taken with the same medical diagnoses and nursing problems. The location used in this research is Koja Regional Hospital, North of Jakarta. Datas are collected through interviews, observation, physical examination and documentation. Validity tests are carried out directly on respondents as the main data source. The data analysis process evaluates the extent of the success of the nursing actions that have been taken in reducing vertigo pain with Brandt Daroff Therapy. Research ethics uses informed consent, anonymity and confidentiality.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Nursing care for postpartum mothers with the risk of infection in the perineal wound

3.1.1 Assessment

The assessment process was carried out on all respondents starting from the respondent's identity data such as name, age, gender, ethnicity, marital status, education and employment. Obstetric history. Then a physical examination was carried out directly on the respondent to collect direct data in the form of a general physical examination of the body, chest and breast, abdomen and anogenital which supports the problem of infection risk. An assessment of daily habit patterns was also carried out to obtain psychological data from respondents. The results of the studies carried out on respondents were strengthened by the results of supporting examinations (laboratory). Collected data from pharmacological management of researchers as supporting data in research.

3.1.2 Nursing Diagnosis

From the results of the assessment carried out on the respondents, nursing diagnoses were obtained, namely Acute Pain (D.0077) related to physical injury agents (episiotomy wounds), Risk of infection (D.0142) related to the effects of invasive procedures (post episiotomy) and Knowledge Deficit (D.0111) was associated with less exposure to information about vulva hygiene and Kegel exercise.

3.1.3 Nursing Intervention

The general nursing plan has been created, adjusted and set at 3x24 hours to make it easier to carry out evaluations and also in accordance with the time for providing nursing care.

3.1.4 Nursing Implementation

In general, the priority nursing action for the nursing diagnosis raised is the risk of infection, which can be carried out in accordance with the plan that has been prepared, then adjusted to the condition of the respondent in the field. Where in the implementation the researcher collaborated with the room nurse in carrying out nursing actions. Supporting factors for the implementation of nursing are good cooperation between the respondent, the respondent's family, and the room nurse in carrying out nursing actions and also adequate room facilities.

3.1.5 Nursing Evaluation

The evaluation was done based on the condition of the respondents and was made according to the problems in the evaluation, namely by using SOAP (Subjective, Objective, Analysis and Planning). Brandt Daroff exercise was carried out on respondents with a frequency of once a day for 30 seconds which resulted in response and the respondents which resulted in response and the respondents were able to do vulva hygiene independently using binahong leaves and Kegel exercise to help strengthen the vaginal muscles after childbirth and there were no signs of REEDA on the wound episiotomy and the pain scale decreased. Supporting factors for the nursing evaluation were that the respondents were very cooperative, with increased knowledge about caring for infected wounds with correct vulva hygiene of binahong leaves and the discipline of the respondents so that they could reduce the risk of infection in perineal wounds.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The postpartum period is begun after the birth of the placenta and ends when the uterine organs return to their original state or pre-pregnancy state. The postpartum period starts from 2 hours after the birth of the placenta to 6 weeks (42 days) after that. During normal delivery, mother can experience injuries to the perineum due to an episiotomy or a tear in the birth canal. Perineal laceration is a wound in the muscular area covered by skin between the vaginal introitus and anus caused by tears due to childbirth. Binahong leaves contain antimicrobials which are theoretically effective in healing wounds by preventing infection and Kegel exercise to help strengthen the vaginal muscles after childbirth. In the nursing diagnosis formulation, Acute Pain (D.0077) is related to a physical injury agent (episiotomy wound). The nursing action planning stage is prepared based on problems found in the field. The implementation of nursing actions can be carried out based on plans that have been prepared and determined, the actions are adjusted to the circumstances or condition of the respondent. From the nursing evaluation, the respondent was able to carry out vulva hygiene independently using binahong leaves and Kegel exercise to help strengthen the vaginal muscles after delivery and revealed that there were no signs of REEDA in the episiotomy wound and the pain scale had decreased.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author would like to thank the Director of RSUD Koja, North of Jakarta and his staff who have given permission to do research activities and the respondents who were willing to provide the required data. Thanks to Harum Nursing Academy, Jakarta which has funded this research activity.

6. REFERENCES

- 1) Agnes Batmomolin, S. K. N. M. K., Ivonne A. V Gasper, S. K. N. M. K., Ana B. Montol., S. P. M. S., Bdn. Desi Nindya Kirana, S. S. T. M. K., Anita Damayanti Lubis, S. T. K. M. K., Keb, D. I. S. P. S. S. T. B. M. T., Nila Hayati, S. S. T. M. K. M. M. K., Nurdahliana, S. K. M. M. K. C. H. E., Juli Oktalia, S. S. T. A., & Nonce Nova Legi, S. S. T. M. S. (2023). Postpartum Anthology. Indo Library Media. <https://Books.Google.Co.Id/Books?Id=Arfkeaaaqbaj>
- 2) Alfin Nurrido. (2022). Signs of Infection in Wounds. Directorate General of Health Care.
- 3) Aprilia, R. (2023). The Effect of Boiled Water from Binahong Leaves (*Anredera Cordifolia*) on Healing Perineal Wounds in Postpartum Women in Pmb "M" Bogor Regency in 2022. National University.
- 4) Astuti, D. L. P. (2021). Description of Premature Rupture of Membranes at Surya Husadha Hospital Denpasar in 2020. Midwifery Department 2021.
- 5) Bararah, T. (2015). Nursing Care Complete Guide to Becoming a Professional Nurse. Jakarta: Pustakaraya Achievement.
- 6) Crystanty, I. E. (2018). Case Study of Giving Virgin Coconut Oil in Healing Perineal Wounds (Inflammatory Phase) of Post Partum Mothers with Second Degree Episiotomy at Mrs. Bps. Sri Mulatsih, Taman District, Sidoarjo Regency. Muhammadiyah University Surabaya.
- 7) Dewi, N. P. D. J. S. (2021). Overview of Post Partum Maternal Care at Tabanan III Community Health Center in 2021. Health Polytechnic Ministry of Health Denpasar Nursing Department 2021.
- 8) Ekasari, D. J., Yunita, P., & Hafid, R. A. (2022). Vulva Hygiene Management with Perineal Wound Healing. Midwifery Zone: Batam University Midwifery Study Program, 12(2).
- 9) Fadli, R. (2023). Get to know the benefits of binahong leaves for health and how to process them. Hellodoc.
- 10) Fitri, D. H., Umarianti, T., & Wijayanti, W. (2023). The Effectiveness of Warm Compresses in Reducing the Intensity of Labor Pain in the Active Phase of First Stage. Permas Scientific Journal: Kendal Stikes Scientific Journal, 13(4), 1189–1200.
- 11) Gusnimar, R., Veri, N., & Mutiah, C. (2021). The Effect of Boiled Water from Binahong Leaves in Accelerating Healing of Perineal Wounds During the Postpartum Period. Cell Journal of Health Research, 8(1), 15–23.
- 12) Ifadah, E., Nurhidayah, I., Tyas, M. D. C., Azizah, L. N., Suryani, L., Syamsiah, N., Abdillah, A., Sutini, N. K., Suryanto, Y., & Rudini, R. (2023). Nursing Actions: Endocrine, Immunological, Digestive and Urinary Systems. Pt. Sonpedia Publishing Indonesia. <https://Books.Google.Co.Id/Books?Id=Tkfkeaaaqbaj>
- 13) Mardha, M. S., Syafitri, E., & Handayani, D. (2023). The Effect of Giving Boiled Water from Binahong Leaves (*Anredera Cordifolia*) on Healing Perineal Wounds in Postpartum Women. Journal Of Pharmaceutical And Sciences, 1363–1368.

- 14) Maryunani, A. (2015). Latest Care for Caesarean Section (Sc) Wounds and Obstetric Wounds. Team.
- 15) Mercy Joice Kaparang, S. K. M. M. K., & et al. (2023). Anthology of Midwifery Care During Postpartum and Breastfeeding. Indo Library Media. <https://books.google.co.id/books?id=Yopceaaaqbaj>
- 16) Mertasari, L., & Sugandini, W. (2023). Postpartum Care and Breastfeeding. Pt. Rajagrafindo Persada - Rajawali Press. <https://books.google.co.id/books?id=9zrdeaaaqbaj>
- 17) Metasari, D., Kando, S. B., & Rahmawati, D. T. (2023). Analysis of the Implementation of Kegel Exercises on Episiotomy Wound Healing in Postpartum Women in Bengkulu City. *Udayana Medical Journal*, 9(02), 214–221.
- 18) Permatasari, N. Z. (2018). Descriptive Study of Vulva Hygiene Practices in Adolescent Girls at the Girls' Nurul Burhany I Mranggen Islamic Boarding School, Demak Regency. Muhammadiyah University of Semarang.
- 19) PPNI, T. P. (2017). Indonesian Nursing Diagnosis Standards. Jakarta: Ppni Central Management Board.
- 20) PPNI, T. P. (2018). Indonesian Nursing Intervention Standards. In Ppni Central Management Board
- 21) PPNI, T. P. S. D. (2018). Indonesian Nursing Outcome Standards (1st Ed.). Central Executive Board of the Indonesian National Professional Nurses Association. Library Achievement.
- 22) Purwaningrum, R. B., & Herawati, I. (2022). The Effect of Kegel Exercises on Healing Perineal Wounds in Post Partum Mothers. *Wellness And Healthy Magazine*, 4(2), 165–170.
- 23) Raka, I. M., & Sari, N. K. (2022). Benefits of Boiled Binahong (*Anredera Cordifolia*) Leaves for Lowering Blood Sugar Levels. Nem Publishers. <https://books.google.co.id/books?id=Z7uzeaaaqbaj>
- 24) Rukmana, H. R., & Yudirachaman, H. H. (2024). Farm Bigbook: Cultivation and Postharvest of Featured Medicinal Plants. Andi Publisher. <https://books.google.co.id/books?id=Ljx2eaaaqbaj>
- 25) S., N. . & T. (2016). Midwifery Care for Postpartum Women. Salemba Medika.
- 26) Sari, S. N. T., Wagiyo, S. K., Kep, N. M., Mat, S., Skp, K. P. L., Sapartinah, T., & Sari, S. N. T. (2022). Nursing Care Risk of Infection in Post Partum Mothers with Perineal Sutures.
- 27) Sulisnani, A. N. A., Utami, A., Nurlaila, N., Septiani, V., & Ice, N. (2022). The Effectiveness of Kegel Exercises on the Healing Process of Perineal Wounds in Post Partum Mothers. *Proceedings of the National Seminar and Cfp Midwifery, Ngudi Waluyo University*, 1(2), 1029–1038.
- 28) Yayah Hilmiah, D. M. N. F. F. N. T. R. D. S. M. (2023). Postpartum Care in the Family. Download Library. https://books.google.co.id/books?id=O6_Neaaaqbaj